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Enhanced Battery Control Using Smell Agent Optimized Pi For Two-Stage Power Systems

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ABSTRACT

This research proposes the development of an optimized proportional Integral controller for two-stage battery system using Smell Agent Optimization (SAO) algorithm. Battery management involves regulating charging and discharging processes to maximize efficiency and extend battery lifespan. Proportional Integral (PI) control technique is one of the classical control techniques that have been widely used for the regulation of battery charging and discharging processes. However, PI controller is able to stabilize the battery state of charge to some certain degree, but the root mean square error (RMSE) with respect to battery current control is not satisfactory due to uncertainties during the process of charging and discharging processes of battery. Thus, there is need to improve on the performance achieved with PI control technique in order to maximize efficiency and extend battery lifespan. To address this, this research proposes an approach based on an optimized proportional Integral controller for two-stage battery system in order to enhance the regulation of battery charging and discharging processes while preventing energy overloads or deep discharges which would compromise the life of the battery itself. This problem will be addressed in this research by developing optimized proportional Integral controller for two-stage battery system using Smell Agent Optimization (SAO) algorithm. Firstly, model of bi-directional converter for charging the two-stage battery system model was developed in Simulink. Then the PI controller was designed and the cost function was formulated in terms of PI gains before applying on the developed Simulink model. The performance of the developed optimized PI system was evaluated using battery reference control of in RMSE as performance metrics. The simulation results when the nominal current and load voltage were within the desired range of 20A and 48V showed that the developed SAO-PI obtained RMSE of 0.721. This resulted in 7.21% improvement in RMSE when compared to that of SISO-Fuzzy logic technique. This implies that the developed SAO-PI has a good battery reference control. This clearly shows the effectiveness of the developed controller in stabilizing the system as fast as possible. All simulations were implemented in MATLAB R2022b.

Keywords: Optimized Proportional Integral Controller, two-stage battery system, Smell Agent Optimization (SAO), Battery management, Proportional Integral (PI), root mean square error (RMSE).

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Electric vehicles (EV) and renewable energy systems (RES) have grown rapidly due in part to the need to lessen environmental pollution and reliance on nonrenewable resources (Sarsia et al., 2023). Since they are regarded as the main energy storage source for RESs and EVs, batteries are crucial. Lithium-ion batteries (LIB) are especially promising due to their superior performance and steadily declining cost. However, LIBs are typically subjected to a variety of abusive circumstances and function in a tough environment. In addition to causing anomalous temperature rises that might result in gas production or even thermal runaway, combustion, and explosion, overloading, external heat transfer, overly fast charging, and internal/external short circuits can also shorten battery life. As a result, batteries need to be properly handled to guarantee their security and increase their lifespan. A battery management system (BMS) is needed to not only monitor all kinds of battery states, but also to ensure that battery performance meets the demands of the vehicle throughout the battery service life (Costa et al., 2021).

A key aspect of battery management involves regulating charging and discharging processes to maximize efficiency and extend battery lifespan. Several control systems have been developed to automate the battery control based on proportional integral derivative, fuzzy logic controller, sliding mode controller, and proportional integral controller (Lee et al., 2021)

Proportional Integral (PI) controller is one of the conventional techniques commonly used for battery control due to their simplicity and effectiveness. The battery has a hysteretic loop and nonlinear charging circuit. The traditional PI setting approach involves a complex setup procedure. The empirical formula and several experiments require the PID settings to be adjusted. Realizing the perfect parameter setting is challenging. The control system has a long response time and a large overshoot, and it cannot meet the requirements of the current control (Zainurin et al., 2021). The accurate control of the charging parameters (charge voltage and current) of the lithium battery can shorten the charging time, improve the charging efficiency of the battery, prolong the service life and reduce the cost. Therefore, it is of great significance to the PI parameter tuning of the battery charging circuit (Liu et al., 2022).

In this research, an optimized proportional Integral controller for two-stage batteries model will be designed in order to enhance performance in regulating charging and discharging processes. In order to achieve enhance the performance of the PI, the PI gains was optimized using Smell Agent Optimization (SAO) algorithm.

2.0 Problem Statement/Justification

Battery management system (BMS) is vital for the safe operation of any device that uses lithium-ion batteries. Battery management involves regulating charging and discharging processes to maximize efficiency and extend battery lifespan. Proportional Integral (PI) control technique is one of the classical control techniques that have been widely used for the regulation of battery charging and discharging processes. However, PI controller is able to stabilize the battery state of charge to some certain degree, but the root mean square error (RMSE) with respect to battery current control is not satisfactory due to uncertainties during the process of charging and discharging processes of battery. Thus, there is need to improve on the performance achieved with PI control technique in order to maximize efficiency and extend battery lifespan. To address this, this research presents an approach based on an optimized proportional Integral controller for two-stage battery system in order to enhance the regulation of battery charging and discharging processes while preventing energy overloads or deep discharges which would compromise the life of the battery itself. To achieve this, a Meta-heuristic approach using the Smell Agent Optimization (SAO) technique will be used to optimize the gain parameters of PI in a well formulated optimization problem. This is to ensure the safe range of energy management amidst evolving energy landscapes and technological advancements.

3.0 Objectives

In order to achieve the stated aim of the research, the following objectives are set.

1. To develop the Simulink model of two-stage battery model.
2. To develop an optimized SAO-PI controller for the developed the Simulink model (1).

3.To evaluate the performance of the developed system with the research of Muritala *et al.*, (2024) using DC voltage regulation, battery voltage and battery reference control as performance metrics

4.0 Literature Review

Some research relevant to the study are reviewed and presented in this section. These literatures include the previous works on battery management system, different battery control techniques and optimization algorithms used for battery management system (BMS).

Kumar & Dinesh., (2020) presented the electric vehicle's battery management concept and execution. Preventing misuse and damage to the battery cells was the primary goal of the project. In their work, implementation of active clamp forward converter for active cell balancing, design a new BMS platform based on available dedicated integrated circuits and microcontrollers targeting fast sampling, high accuracy, low consumption and low cost were carried out. The BMS topology and active forward converter was simulated in Or CAD, TINA software and MATLAB Simulink software. The simulation of the active forward converter showed that for an input voltage of 40V the output voltage was 3.3V, with an efficiency of 90%. The ripple in the converter is limited to less than 5%. The BMS topology is reviewed and the PCB was printed, then the PCB is tested with connecting battery stack for both charging and discharging process of active cell balancing

Ibrahim *et al.*, (2022) designed an artificial pancreas based on genetic-fuzzy proportional Integral (fuzzy-PI) technique for two-Stage battery Control. Since the fuzzy-PI controller only works with linear systems, the proposed method linearized the Bi-directional conveter model using a gap metric before using it .The proposed method used the triangle membership function with L, M, and H as its linguistic variables. The recommended controller outperformed the other controller in terms of DC voltage regulation, battery voltage and battery reference control after the proposed two stage battery model was simulated and the results were compared with classic fuzzy-PI. But the reported battery voltage was rather high

Singh *et al.*, (2023) design and control of a two-stage onboard battery charger (OBC) for the low-voltage electric vehicle (LVEVs). The charger in this study has a high power factor and can function over a broad variety of AC input voltages. A bridgeless AC-DC converter with constant input current characteristics at the front end is used in the developed charger. An isolated Cuk DC-DC converter was used at the charger's back end to implement and regulate various battery charging modes using constant voltage (CV) and constant current (CC) charging profiles. Battery current control with regard to DC voltage regulation, battery voltage, and battery reference control are some of the parameters on which the performance is compared with other modern power factor correction (PFC) topologies. The overall operational analysis and efficacy of the design were confirmed through both simulations and experimental implementation.

Muritala *et al.*, (2024) designed the Single Input Interval Type 2 Fuzzy Logic Proportional Integral (SIIT2FLPI) controller, designed for regulating a battery using a two-stage control approach. In the proposed technique, the lithium battery model was designed in MATLAB/Simulink prior to using the SIIT2FL-PI controller in order to enhance the regulation procedures for charging and discharging batteries. Since it can only work on linear system. The proposed two-stage battery model was simulated and the result was compared using a traditional PI controller where the proposed controller outperformed the other controller in terms of RMSE of 31% improvement in battery current control with respect to DC voltage regulation, battery voltage and battery reference control.

From the reviewed literatures, it is evident that the regulation of battery charging and discharging control for a lithium battery have received substantial research attention, resulting in the creation of several battery management system controllers, including PID, IBC, LQR, FLC, and SMC controllers. The majority of the research attempted to address the issue of either battery voltage or high DC voltage control. However, the effect of longer reference battery control required for effectively controlling the charging and discharging processes. Therefore, developing an optimized proportional Integral controller for two-stage battery system using Smell Agent Optimization (SAO) algorithm for the control of battery management system is the foundation upon which this study is based.

5.0 METHODOLOGY

In this section, step-by-step procedures leading to the implementation of the stated objectives are discussed based on the following assumptions:

5.1 Development Simulink model of Two-stage Battery Model

Figure 1: Model of a Boost Converter (Kumar *et al.*, 2019)

The transfer capability of boost converter depends upon the inductor (L_{boost}) and capacitor (C_{boost}) as shown in Figure 1 The output voltage (V_{DC}), L_{boost} and C_{boost} value is obtained as (Kumar *et al.*, 2019):

$$V_{DC} = \frac{1}{1-D_b} V_{PV} \quad (1)$$

$$L_{boost} = \frac{V_{DC} D_b}{\Delta I_L f} \quad (2)$$

$$C_{boost} = \frac{V_{PV} D_b}{R_o \Delta V_{PV} f} \quad (3)$$

Where V_{PV} , $\Delta I_{L,f}$, R_o and R_o are the input voltage, inductor ripple current, switching frequency, capacitor ripple voltage and output impedance of boost converter respectively.

Equations (1) to (4), which describe current, SOC, voltage, and amplitude, respectively, are the mathematical model of the two-stage battery system. The model was modeled in Simulink for both the charging and discharging modes. To represent the boost converter, as shown in the Figure below, equations (1) to (2) were also utilized. Figure 2 displays the two-stage battery's Simulink model after it was developed.

Figure 2: Simulink Model of Charging and Discharging.

Table 1 shows the values of Lithium battery model parameters used in this work.

Table 1: Lithium Battery Parameters (Muritala et al., 2024)

Parameter	Value	Unit
Nominal voltage	0.072	V
Rated capacity	0.0005	Ah
Initial state of charge	0.00021	%
Battery response time	0.5	S
Battery nominal discharge current	0.002	A

5.2 Development SAO-PI controller for the Two-stage Battery system

To develop the PI based two-stage battery control system; there is the need to obtain the best possible combination of the PI gain parameters.

5.2.1 To designed PI controller in MATLAB/Simulink

The control scheme was developed in this section. It is made up of the integral and proportional parts. The PI control law function can be state as:

$$u(t) = K_p e(t) + K_i \int e(t) dt \quad (4)$$

The resulting Simulink model is showing below:

Figure 3: Simulink Model of PI Controller.

The Simulink diagram of the PI controller with two (2) controller parameters (k_p and k_i).is shown in Figure 3.The Smell Agent Optimization Algorithm (SAO) was created in order to determine the PI

controller's ideal parameters. This algorithm's goal function is based on the controller gains (k_p and k_i), which are calculated separately.

5.2.2 Formulation of optimization problem based on the Parameters obtained

The control law in equation (4) was used to formulate the given weighting factor into an objective function in order to produce an optimized weigh for the controller input. The optimization problem's goal is to maximize gains while minimizing weight. k_p and k_i , for integral time absolute error minimization between the control input $u(t)$. On the basis of equation (4), the cost function was developed. The boundaries for the system variables were determined by considering the range derived from the implementation of PI without utilizing SAO. The following constraints are used to select the best solution:

$$4 < k_p < 4.5 \tag{5}$$

$$43 < k_i < 44 \tag{6}$$

Therefore, k_p and k_i are the weighting factor's parameters that need to be optimized in order to fulfill the goal.

5.2.3 Optimization of the weighting factor using SAO

The SAO algorithm was employed in this research to optimize the cost function parameters. Equation (4) serves as evaluation criteria for the optimality of the results obtained by SAO. The flowchart for evaluating the cost function using SAO is given in Figure 5.

Figure 4: Flowchart of Objective Function Cost Evaluation

Figure 4 shows the flowchart for evaluating the weighting factor cost. In the first step, a population of size N is created. Afterward, the SAO selection procedure is executed in a manner that seeks the ideal parameter combination to produce the greatest result. It optimizes the cost function until the termination criteria are met. Table 2 provides the SAO parameters used in this study.

Table 2: SAO Parameter

S/N	Parameters	Symbol	Value	Unit.
1.	Population	N	50
2.	Dimension	D	3
3.	Iteration	Itr	10
4.	Step Movement	SM	2.5	M

5.2.4 Simulation of the system model with the developed SAO-PI controller

Figure 5 shows the close loop system developed in Simulink/MATLAB that was used to simulate the developed PI with the two-stage battery under various initial circumstances (IC).

Figure 5: Simulink Model of two-stage battery system using Optimized PI

Figure 5 showed the developed Simulink model an optimized SAO-PI controller for two-stage battery system. The model made up of five compartments: the buck Dc converter model, PI controller, lithium battery model and bus bar which output to the workspace. The best gain parameters was obtained using SAO algorithm. Using the signal builder block, the intended reference that is, the battery voltage regulation value of 26.84V was produced. Scope blocks were used to produce the system's response states.

6.0 RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Presented in this section contains the results obtained when SISO Fuzzy logic technique was applied within a specific range of charging and discharging of battery.

6.1 Proportional Integral Parameter Selection

PI controller was optimized to use SAO to find the best gains; ten iterations later, the optimal parameters were discovered as below.

Table 3: Optimal Parameters of PI

SAO Parameters	Value
Cost Function	1.4451
K_p	-3.0215
K_i	43.610

Figure 7 below shows the convergence plot when SAO was applied on the formulated cost function in equation.

Figure 7: SAO Convergence plot on Benchmark System

Figure 7 shows the convergence plot when SAO was applied on the PI cost function in order to obtain optimal gains parameters. It was observed from the Figure 7 above that, the algorithm converged at the 4th iterations.

6.2 Simulation Results of SAO-PI and SISO-Fuzzy with the Two-stage Battery Model

The outcomes of the simulation for each of Smell Agent Optimization Proportional Integral (SAO-PI) control and Single Input Single Output Fuzzy Logic (SISO-Fuzzy Logic) control with two-stage battery system displayed in Figures 3 and 5 were acquired by taking into account the nominal current of 22A. The response of the battery current is shown in Figure 8

Figure 8: Battery Current

Figure 8 illustrates the battery current, which indicates the rate of energy transfer to or from the battery when it is being charged and discharged. The reference current shown represents the desired trajectory that the developed SAO-PI controller aims to track in the initial control stage, serving as the

optimal target current. Monitoring the battery current is crucial for evaluating the state of charge, assessing battery performance, and maintaining the overall system's stability and safety. As seen in Figure 2, the error between the battery voltage and its reference voltage and the error between the DC voltage and the common load voltage define the SAO-PI controller's output.

Figure 9 shows the graphs of state of charge of battery obtained from simulation

Figure 9: State of Charge (SOC) of the Battery

The battery SOC, which is represented as a percentage of its total capacity and measures the amount of electrical energy stored in the battery at any one time, is shown in Figure 9. This value reflects the remaining charge and indicates how much energy is available for use. As observed from the figure, the proposed SAO-PI controller enables a quicker SOC response during both the charging and discharging phases of the voltage switch controller. Unlike the Single Input Single Output (SISO-Fuzzy Logic) two-stage battery control technique, which also, ensures that the SOC during the charging and discharging state of the voltage switch controller within 79.99% - 80%

Figure 10 shows the graphs of load voltage obtained from simulation.

Figure 10: Load Voltage

The performance of the SISO fuzzy logic-based controller and the SAO-PI controller with respect to the load voltage is shown in Figure 10. As shown, the SAO-PI controller successfully tracks the reference voltage of 48V and stabilizes the battery system within 0.04 seconds. This highlights the SAO-PI controller's ability to deliver superior system performance under critical load conditions. In comparison, the SISO fuzzy logic-based controller also manages to follow the reference signal and achieves steady-

state operation at 0.065 seconds, enabling continuous monitoring of the load voltage and adjusting the battery's discharge rate to keep the voltage around the desired 48V range.

Figure 11 shows the graphs of voltage source switch obtained from simulation.

Figure 11: Voltage Source Switch

The voltage source switch is depicted in Figure 11 during the battery system's charging and discharging operations. Figure 11 showed that the charging process is started when the switch is switched on (one), allowing the battery to accept voltage from the voltage source. This enables the battery to sustain its state of charge (SOC) and restore its energy reserves. On the other hand, when the source voltage switch is turned off (zero), it disconnects the battery from the voltage source, preventing further charging. This is important to avoid overcharging the battery, leading to degradation, and reducing lifespan. Additionally, turning off the source voltage switch during certain conditions may be necessary to conserve energy or prevent damage to the battery system.

6.3 Performance Comparison of the Developed SAO-PI based and SISO-Fuzzy

The performance of the controllers for the two-stage battery control system was assessed on the basis of root mean square error (RMSE) as reported in Muritala *et al.*, (2024). The performance of the developed Smell Agent Optimization Proportional Integral (SAO-PI) controller and SISO-Fuzzy logic controller based on DC voltage regulation, battery voltage and battery reference control with respect to the performance metric were presented in Table 4

Table 4: Performance Comparison between the Developed SAO-PI and SISO-Fuzzy Logic Schemes

Performance Specification	Controller		Percentage Improvement (%)
	Developed SAO-PI	SISO-Fuzzy Logic	
DC Voltage Regulation	0.008	0.008	–
Battery Voltage	0.02	0.02	–
Battery Reference Control	0.7130	0.769	7.21%

Table 4 summarizes the performance comparison of the developed SAO-PI and that of SISO-Fuzzy logic reported in the work of Muritala *et al.*, (2024). It can be observed from the Table 4 above that, the developed SAO-PI has the overall improvement of good battery reference control of 7.21% in RMSE when compared to the work reported by (Muritala *et al.*, 2024).

7.0 CONCLUSION

This research has presented the development an optimized proportional Integral controller for two-stage battery model. In Simulink, a two-stage battery model was developed PI and GGO were then used to adjust the gain parameters in an optimal battery control scheme. The MATLAB/Simulink software was

utilized to the simulation in MATLAB2022b for the battery discharging rate to maintain the load voltage within the desired range of 48V. The performance evaluation of the results was carried out and compared to the two-stage battery system developed by (Muritala *et al.*,2022) in terms of root mean square error (RMSE).

The simulation results reveal that the developed GGO-PI has the overall improvement of good battery reference control of 7.21% in RMSE when compared to the work reported by (Muritala *et al.*, 2024)

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